

VIBRATION FREQUENCY DESIGN AND STUDY OF COMPOSITE FUSELAGE STRUCTURE

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INTRODUCTION

The influence of various physical properties of composite materials on the natural vibration frequency of the cylindrical shell is studied. On this basis, an equivalent design method is proposed.

Firstly, an equivalent stiffness model is established aiming at resolving two typical problems about beam-type vibration frequencies and positions on modal nodes.

Secondly, through the design of experiments, the effects of the elastic modulus and Poisson's ratio of the composite on the beam-type vibration frequency of the cylindrical shell are studied, correlations among these parameters and natural frequencies are also discussed.

Finally, genetic algorithm is used to design the composite fuselage structural layout in detail based on the equivalent stiffness model.

EQUIVALENT STIFFNESS MODEL

Figure (a) and (b) show the equivalent stiffness model.

The frequency relationship between the equivalent stiffness model and the fuselage structure is expressed as follow.

$$\frac{f_M}{f_R} = \frac{\sqrt{\frac{E_M I_M / L_M^3}{M_M}}}{\sqrt{\frac{E_R I_R / L_R^3}{M_R}}} \Rightarrow \sqrt{\frac{E_R I_{Ri}}{\rho_M A_M L_M + M_{KM}}} = \sqrt{\frac{E_M I_{Mi}}{\rho_M A_M L_M + M_{KM}}} \cdot \left(\frac{L_R}{L_M}\right)^3 \cdot \frac{f_R}{f_M}$$

$K_{Ri(x/z)}$ is defined as the stiffness index of the fuselage

$$K_{Rix} = \sqrt{\frac{E_M I_{Miy}}{\rho_M A_M L_M + M_{KM}}} \cdot \left(\frac{L_R}{L_M}\right)^3 \cdot \frac{f_R}{f_M}$$

$$K_{Riz} = \sqrt{\frac{E_M I_{Miz}}{\rho_M A_M L_M + M_{KM}}} \cdot \left(\frac{L_R}{L_M}\right)^3 \cdot \frac{f_R}{f_M}$$

Fuselage stiffness indexes are shown in this figure, unit is mm.

INFLUENCE OF MATERIAL PARAMETERS

Error1: First-order beam-type vibration
 Error2: Second-order beam-type vibration
 Figure (a) shows the influence of $\sqrt{1 - \nu_x \cdot \nu_\theta}$ on error of calculated values.

Figure (b) shows the influence of $E_x - E_\theta$ on the error of calculated values, figure (c) shows the influence of E_x/E_θ on the error of calculated values.

VERIFICATION

Comparisons between target & calculated values

Frequency	Target value (cycles/time)	Calculated value (cycles/time)	Relative Error
F7	140	138.49	-1.08%
F8	150	149.91	-0.06%
F10	280	268.90	-3.96%
F11	305	277.73	-8.94%

Modal Node	Target value (mm)	Calculated value (mm)	Relative Error
7S1	920	902	-0.45%
7S2	3080	3098	0.45%
8S1	890	872	-0.45%
8S2	3120	3137	0.43%
10S1	490	495	0.13%
10S2	2000	2010	0.25%
10S3	3510	3514	0.10%
11S1	500	500	0.00%
11S2	1990	2000	0.25%
11S3	3480	3490	0.25%

CONCLUSION & DISCUSSION

a) The influence of the parameters of the anisotropic material on the beam-type vibration frequency of the cylindrical shell is discussed. It is found that the frequency error has an obvious exponential relationship with $E_x - E_\theta$ and E_x/E_θ . By specifying the error range, the value range of the respective elastic modulus can be constrained, thereby constraining the layup design of the composite material.

b) For higher precision design requirements, besides adding stiffness index constraint, other design criteria could be considered, such as strength criterion, damage tolerance criterion, etc.